

TEACHING GRAMMAR THROUGH READING

Pirmamatova Dilnoza Muhammadali kizi
Samarkand State Institute of Foreign Languages
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6645846>

ARTICLE INFO

Received: 28th May 2022
Accepted: 02nd June 2022
Online: 05th June 2022

KEY WORDS

reading skills, speaking skills, vocabulary knowledge

ABSTRACT

There is an increasingly high relationship between reading and speaking skills. There is no question that people who develop large reading vocabularies tend to develop large speaking vocabularies. Indeed, reading power relies on continuous improvement in vocabulary knowledge that provides communication. The importance of word knowledge, which facilitates speaking skills, has been a major resource in the development of reading skills. Therefore fostering improvement in word knowledge through wide reading has the potential for fostering improvement in speaking skills. This article focuses on how printed words relate to spoken words and finally how reading contributes to speech.

INTRODUCTION

“Where there is little reading there will be little language learning. The student who wants to learn English will have to read himself into a knowledge of it unless he can move into an English environment” (Bright and McGregor, 1970, p.52).

Reading outside the classroom is the most significant influence on oral communication ability. Students who read a lot are more likely to speak well. Students through reading develop in both fluency and accuracy of expression in their speaking. Davies and Pearse (2000) stresses the importance of communication as: “Real success in English teaching and learning is when the learners can actually

communicate in English inside and outside the classroom.¹”

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Speaking is being capable of speech, expressing or exchanging thoughts through using language. “Speaking is a productive aural/oral skill and it consists of producing systematic verbal utterances to convey meaning (Nunan, 2003, p.48).” (Harmer, 2001) notes down that from the communicative point of view, speaking has many different aspects including two major categories – accuracy, involving the correct use of vocabulary, grammar and pronunciation practised through controlled and guided activities; and, fluency, considered to be ‘the ability to

¹ Brusch, W. (1991). The role of reading in foreign language acquisition: Designing an experimental project. *ELT Journal*, 45(2), 156-163. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/elt/45.2.156>

keep going when speaking spontaneously'. Bygate (1991, p.3), also emphasizes knowledge of the language, and skill in using this knowledge for an effective communication. Language knowledge and skill in using it, are considered two fundamental elements of an effective communication².

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Reading is one of the most effective ways of foreign language learning. Reading simply is the interpretation of a written message. Walter R. Hill (1979, p.4) briefly defines reading as what the reader does to get the meaning he needs from contextual resources.

Reading is a fluent process of readers combining information from a text and their own background knowledge to build meaning and the goal of reading is comprehension (Nunan, 2003, p.68). The ability to read requires that the reader draw information from a text and combine it with information and expectations that the reader already has (Grabe, Stoller, 2001, p.187).

Figure 1. Definition of reading (David Nunan. *Practical English Language Teaching*. 2003. p. 72) Hedge (2003) writes the goals of learners' in a reading process as:

- The ability to read a wide range of texts in English.
- Building a knowledge of language

² Bygate, M. (2011). *Speaking*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.

which will facilitate reading ability

- Building schematic knowledge
- The ability to adapt the reading style according to reading purpose (skimming, scanning)
- Developing an awareness of the structure of written texts in English
- Taking a critical stance to the contexts of the texts

In a reading process six component skills have been suggested. Among these knowledge fields vocabulary and structural knowledge which are acquired through reading, influence learner's speaking achievement³.

- 1) Automatic recognition skills
- 2) Vocabulary and structural knowledge
- 3) Formal discourse structure knowledge
- 4) Content/world background knowledge
- 5) Synthesis and evaluation skills/strategies
- 6) Metacognitive knowledge and skills monitoring (Grabe, 1991, p.379).

How do these component skills contribute to speaking skills? Anne Lazaraton (2001, p.104) suggests that oral communication is based on four dimensions or competences: grammatical competence (phonology, vocabulary, word and sentence formation ...); sociolinguistic competence (rules for interaction, social meanings); discourse competence (cohesion and how sentences are linked together); and strategic competence (compensatory strategies to use in difficult strategies).

³ Eskey, D. (2005). Reading in a Second Language. In E. Hinkel (Ed), *Handbook of research on second language teaching and learning* (pp. 563-580). Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum.

CONCLUSION

Communication without vocabulary will break down. One of the most useful ways to improve your communication skills is extensive reading. Extensive reading will help you to develop your ability to express ideas, whilst also enlarging the size of vocabulary. Vocabulary knowledge is one

of the crucial factors that will influence fluency in speaking. Reading introduces learners to a wider body of language and contexts. Reading helps learners build up better grammar skills. As learners develop stronger reading skills, they develop more sophisticated speaking skills.

References:

1. Brusch, W. (1991). The role of reading in foreign language acquisition: Designing an experimental project. *ELT Journal*, 45(2), 156-163. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1093/elt/45.2.156>
2. Bygate, M. (2011). *Speaking*. Oxford: Oxford University Press.
3. Cunningham, A. E., & Stanovich, K. E. (1998). What Reading does for the Mind. *American Educator*, 8(15). Davies, P., Pearse, E. (2002). *Success in English Teaching*. Shanghai: Shanghai Foreign Language Education Press.
4. Dole, A. J., Sloan, C., & Trathen, W. (1995). Teaching Vocabulary within the Context of Literature. *Journal of Reading*, 38(6), 452-460.
5. Dubin, F., & Olshtain, E. (1977). *Facilitating Language Learning: A Guidebook for the ESL/EFL Teacher*. N.Y: McGraw: Hill International Book Company.
6. Eskey, D. (2005). Reading in a Second Language. In E. Hinkel (Ed), *Handbook of research on second language teaching and learning* (pp. 563-580). Mahwah, NJ: Lawrence Erlbaum.